

The Role Of Servant Leadership In Promoting Intellectual Capital: An Analytical Study Of A Sample Of The Views Of Some Employees At Kufa University

Ahmed Fadhil Salman, Ihsan Abdulmeer Azeez, Hayder Jasim Obaid, Mohanad Hameed Yasir

Article Info

Article History

Received:
August 19, 2020

Accepted:
October 15, 2020

Keywords

Servant leadership,
intellectual capital, Kufa
University.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.4091514

Abstract

The literature suggests that leadership positively affects the overall performance of organizations, as the search results show that the Servant leadership virtuous characteristics of its indicators have been to a degree, The administrative Servant leadership in educational institutions is high, because the administrative leader contributes to To obtain the necessary qualifications for his work with him. It encourages others to take the lead Initiative. Studies also pointed to intellectual capital, which leads to easy access to customers and investors, thereby enhancing the overall performance of organizations. Tests for this study will determine whether the Servant leadership is performing To promote intellectual capital, In this study, the relationship between the Servant leadership of the Khidmah, which was formed by six indicators, was examined: Conceptual skills, empowerment, concern for subordinates for development and success, acting ethic, emotional treatment and commitment to community development and its relationship to intellectual capital. A random sample of the staff of Kufa University was taken and made up of (127)staff members. Hypotheses were tested using the Statistical Program (SPSS V20), which found that Servant leadership practices are positively reflected in the organization's retention of intellectual capital. A positive impact on the Servant leadership of intellectual capital has been achieved, and the research organization must consider the practice of leading methods leading to the retention of intellectual capital.

1. Introduction

Education is of great importance to developed societies as the basic pillar of civilized human-making, The Arab and European countries, big and small, have sought today to change their curricula and develop them to keep pace with the age and to avoid the pattern of censorship and isolation in education. In order to create a growing, effective and conscious atmosphere on which society, the country and the world depend, our parents have harvested what they have learned in their time and created to face today's difficulties with their work, wisdom and consciousness.

In recent decades, organizations around the world have restructured Work to adapt and respond quickly to dynamic and complex work environments, That is by focusing on intangible assets rather than tangible assets to achieve better performance, as many studies and research believe that intangible assets will ensure the survival and competitiveness of the Organization, Here intangible assets refer to intellectual capital, and thus are perceived as an invisible and reliable asset to promote change, and contribute to superior performance and preservation of the Organization over tangible resources (Yusliza et al,2019) .The study therefore attempted to explain the role of leadership in enabling and integrating individual contributions into a collaborative collective effort, as the Servant leadership has attracted considerable interest recently among academics,So it was characterized by a focus on customer growth, empowerment, leadership altruism, empathism, and sense of ethics and community management, the leadership is unique in terms of the leader's view as a (servant) working to meet the needs of customers above their personal needs (Chiniara & Bentein,2017).The world is facing many challenges today to achieve better performance, one of which is the lack of clear and accurate vision of the Servant leadership styles of many management leaders in terms of their relationship with the intellectual capital of business organizations,Many management thinkers believe that leadership will ensure that organizations and businesses stay for long periods with the knowledge and experience they provide, thereby achieving a sustainable competitive advantage in the market. In other words, companies and organizations generally have a problem of making significant progress in domestic and global markets,The research finds that this problem can be described as the intellectual capital variable, i.e. the inability of organizations and companies to keep pace with the evolution of dynamic environments and thus not to provide services appropriate to the customer's

requirements. In light of the above, the problem of research can be formulated in the following question: (Is there an impact on Servant leadership in intellectual capital?).

2. Review the literature

2.1. Servant leadership and intellectual capital

The performance of successful organizations is related to the development of intellectual capital, in order to develop that, regulatory awareness of the concept of knowledge must be raised, so knowledge can be exploited through intellectual capital, which is one of the most important ways to obtain sustainable competitive advantage. Intellectual capital is an intangible asset. It is the sum of knowledge within an organization that can influence observations and environmental management to gain competitive advantage, and it is a non-monetary and non-material resource for organizations that rely on the practical, experience and knowledge to build the value of the organization (Yusliza et al, 2019).

Servant leadership affects the behavior of individuals involved and coordinates efforts to achieve the desired objectives, that is, the activity of the individual who holds a position in the Organization. In other words, the capabilities the leader has to influence the workers and thus gain their obedience to achieve the required goals, it is an activity that must be done in the organization. The jewel of Servant leadership is the care of all subordinates by the leader, who believes that Servant leadership comes from the individual's initiative to serve all the staff of the Organization, and he believes that leadership comes from the feeling of one's wish to serve others, the description of the Servant leadership of the Greenleaf in (1977). It is not an administrative style but a way of life, which starts first with the natural feeling that one wants to serve and then aspires to lead. It also explained it as a leadership-oriented approach that focuses on serving others and sharing power, promoting collective action and a sense of community building within and outside working groups. It also portrayed them as people who embody ethical principles and demonstrate a deep commitment to putting their followers' needs at the heart of their efforts before their personal needs (Chiniara & Benjamin, 2017). Intellectual capital from intangible assets is rare and cannot be easily imitated. These intangible resources and competencies contribute to the organization's superior performance and maintenance over tangible resources and are essential to the organization's survival in dynamic environments (Kengat HARAN, 2019).

Intellectual capital is one of the factors that influence the organization's tendency to enhance its knowledge and skills, often used to change the interaction activities, the organizational environment and knowledge, and thus viewed as an invisible and reliable asset to promote change. Intellectual capital defines procedures to solve an organization's problems, and, through intellectual capital, all organizations seek to learn new activities that closely follow knowledge within their existing capabilities. Moreover, when organizations develop their activities that enhance their skills in finding, identifying and developing solutions to problems, they increase their value in the market (Quan Li & Liu, 2018). Define (Yusoff et al, 2019) Intellectual capital is a collection of well-known actions and things from Before all the staff of the organizations that guarantee the competitive advantage of the organization, Collective knowledge, information, technology, intellectual property rights, experience, organizational learning, competence, and customer relationships capable of creating value for the organization. So Supervisors focus on leadership that is primarily on the well-being of employees and provide these leaders with a psychologically safe environment, striving to demonstrate the full potential of all followers (Bauer et al., 2019).

This type of Servant leadership is different from other commands, in that it is somewhat similar to a server that is interested in other people and the priority of its work is to serve others. Thus, we can see that the main feature that differs between Servant leadership and other Servant leadership is a sense of service to others first before they feel the need to lead people (Andrea et al., 2015). Knowledge that includes ideas, patents, computer programs, trademarks, and design that can be converted into organizational value by considering all non-monetary and non-material resources that are wholly or partly controlled by the Organization and that contribute to the creation of the value of the Organization. He also indicated (El Bannany & Magdi, 2008) that intellectual capital is one of the intangible assets that revolve around the possibility of creating value for organizations, institutions, bodies themselves, information, knowledge, intellectual property and experience that can be used to create wealth. Intellectual capital is therefore an intangible asset and covers the knowledge and experience that skilled employees can use to gain a sustainable competitive advantage by applying some innovative strategies. As (Belizón et al, 2019) has shown the integrated use of intellectual capital in all the intangible assets of the Organization, including processes, the ability to innovate, patents, the tacit knowledge of its members, their abilities, talents and skills, and the recognition of society. We have outlined his contributions to identifying and visualize the intellectual capital variables that determine the generation of scientific knowledge that helps us to establish specific intellectual capital measures. Intellectual capital was defined by (Yong et al, 2019) as the total stock of all types of intangible assets, relationships, knowledge, capabilities, environmental protection and innovation at the individual and organizational levels to gain a competitive advantage. As it is known (AdeSina, 2019) Intellectual capital is the acquisition of knowledge, applied experience, organizational technology, customer relationships, and professional skills that give organizations a competitive advantage in the market.

In the Servant leadership the leader feels responsible for improving his or her staff and is delivering everything that the staff needs (Stollberger et al., 2019). (Eva et al, 2018) sees Servant leadership often focused on the psychological needs of followers, which are a goal in itself, as they know it as the natural feeling that crystallize within a person to serve first and then create a sense of Servant leadership. The concept of Servant leadership is clarified and a new definition of leadership can be given through the following paragraphs: It is (1) a Servant leadership -oriented approach, (2) focusing on the needs of individuals, setting priorities and caring for followers, and (3) redirecting their own attention to serving the community and caring for others within and outside the organization. Thus, a Servant leadership that is so rude does not mean being polite or Friendly, but a sense of strength and sense of self, character and intellectual maturity. According to this definition, those who do not wish to serve others are not eligible for the server administrator. As the leading Servant leadership (Rachmawati&Lantu,2014) has defined service as the means to service others, the theory of leadership has a philosophical basis: (1) the driving motive is service first not Servant leadership. (2) the commander-in-chief serves in the defense of conscience and (3) the self-perception of the service leaders who view themselves as administrators, they are really interested in working followers and an affirmation of their personal well-being. Leadership affects affiliates and changes working relationships with their leader and colleagues in terms of exchange of transactions to social exchange (Chi Zou et al., 2015). The main hypothesis is determined as follows.

H0: There is a significant influence relationship between the Servant leadership and intellectual capital.

2.2. Conceptual skills: We can say that the skills of the leader in knowledge, have an important role in knowing the organization's systems and the needs of subordinates, So that the leader can provide support and support to subordinates, facilitate the work and tasks of others, especially direct subordinates (Howard, 2006). The hypothesis for conceptual skills is therefore determined as follows:

H1: There is a significant, meaningful influence relationship between conceptual skills and intellectual capital.

2.3. Enabling: Empowerment is essentially the delegation of authority/responsibility by the leader to the subordinate, the mere action of empowering the subordinate does not mean ensuring the desired end result, because there are other important variables to be considered by the leader, By providing the necessary facilities to others, encouraging direct subordinates to work, identifying problems and working toward possible solutions to the problem (Appelbaum et al., 2014). For (Gautam&GHIMIRE,2017) structural empowerment depends on the idea that leaders give authority responsibility and information to subordinates, as well as allowing them to participate in workplace decision-making processes. Empowerment arises from the senior management level and moves to staff as well as focuses on how employees feel empowered rather than actually empowered. The enabling hypothesis is therefore determined as follows:

H2: There is a significant and meaningful influence relationship between empowerment and intellectual capital.

2.4. Helping subordinates to develop and succeed: Although the focus is on the concept of in-service relationships between leaders and subordinates in terms of paying attention to the growth of subordinates and giving real attention to the satisfaction of subordinates because of their impact on their results, especially in terms of it, which enables them to acquire the required skills and accomplish the best possible work (TOST&Johnson,2019). While (Pandita et al, 2019) finds that meeting the personal needs of subordinates by the leader, supporting them and providing their requirements increases productive performance and improves their professional skills. Servant leadership plays an important role in creating a kind of trust among leaders and subordinates, because successful leadership emphasizes the use of expressions, information, and clear procedures for direct and other subordinates at the same time, and also meets all the needs and aspirations of subordinates, Their involvement in the decision-making process that you consider to be a priority to be accomplished (Zhao et al., 2015:98). (Koseoglu et al, 2017) also explained that Servant leadership provides opportunities for educators to learn by engaging them in decision-making, and giving priority to problems faced by subordinates during work assigned to them. The hypothesis of helping subordinates to develop and succeed is determined as follows:

H3: There is a significant influence relationship between helping subordinates develop, succeed, and intellectual capital.

2.5. Discreetly: Leaders' dealings with situations that regularly contain ethical issues are both personal and business decision-making, which is the mechanism for dealing with direct and indirect subordinates explicitly, fairly, and honestly (Riley&Kohlbacher,2015). The assumption of acting is therefore determined by morality as follows:

H4: There is a significant, meaningful influence relationship between the conduct of morality and intellectual capital.

2.6. Emotional Processing: Emotions are a response to action, when an event or experience requires us simply to change emotions as information processing systems, i.e. they help us assess what is going on in our environment and decide what reactions to our survival. It is therefore emotional treatment that gives attention to the needs of subordinates and helps them to be provided (Howard, 2006). The hypothesis of emotional treatment is determined as follows:

H5: There is a significant significant influence relationship between emotional treatment and intellectual capital.

2.6 Commitment To Community Development: Societies face a wide range of constraints and deprivation at all levels, whether at the individual level or at the level of economic and technological organizations, and to address and address the needs of these societies, the economic, social and cultural level of these societies (JAGTAP,2019) must be sought to develop and improve. The premise that the commitment to community development is determined by:

H6: There is a significant and meaningful influence relationship between the commitment to community development and intellectual capital.

3·Sample

The sample research covers the(127) employees of Kufa University, a medium-sized educational institution, to obtain a clear picture of this educational institution, researchers need to use standardized data using a laboratory standard.The source of the data is the field reality of Kufah University in Al-Najaf Al-Ashraf governorate/Iraq. It was chosen as an educational institution for the sample search among enterprises because some organizations were trying to hide some important data and information, but the organization chosen as a sample for the search was an organization with complete data, i.e. no data was lost.

4.Methodology and variables

Descriptive entries, which examine the nature of the relationship between study variables and rely on the key steps that start with hypotheses and then discuss the concepts of study, data collection, and then measurement and analysis, then the results are obtained,He thus drew conclusions. The study is based on the descriptive entry, as the hypotheses discussed in the theoretical and practical side are developed, then data will be collected from the worksite of Kufah University in Al-Najaf Al-Ashraf governorate-Iraq, and then data measurement and analysis,The most important findings that demonstrate acceptance or rejection of the study's hypotheses are then drawn up. The study variables formed from two variables, the leading and changing (Servant leadership and intellectual capital), and the leadership indicators formed from six indicators:

5.Testhypotheses

This part of the research is specialized in a statistical presentation, through which the relationships of influence between research change (Servant leadership and intellectual capital) are tested and tested as they are in the study chart, as follows:

5.1.Results of testing the relationships of influence for main and subclaims.

Table(1)shows the results of the test of the influence relationship between the Servant leadership and intellectual capital on the basis of the results of the simple regression determination, assuming an interrelationship between the true value of the leadership (x) and intellectual capital (y) and expressed in the following equation:

$$Y = a + \beta X$$

This equation shows that intellectual capital is a function of the true value of Servant leadership that the estimates and statistical indicators of this equation were calculated at the scale of the study sample of (127)the simple regression equation of the relationship between the two study changes was as follows:

$$\text{Intellectual capital} = (2.422) + (0.658) \text{ Servant leadership}$$

The variance (anovh) was analyzed for the two variables and the results were as in table (1).

Table (1) Contrast analysis (ANOVA) of the Servant leadership between leadership and intellectual capital.

Contrast source	degree of freedom	Sum of squares	The average of squares	F	Sig.
-----------------	-------------------	----------------	------------------------	---	------

regression	1	31.896	31.896	13	0.000
Standard error	126	6.025	.044		
Total of all	127	37.921	31.896		

Source: ECalculator Results.

The transaction table referred to the values indicated and as follows:

Table (2) The results of the test of an influence relationship between the Servant leadership and intellectual capital.

model	Non-standard transactions		Standard transactions	T	Sig.
	Beta coefficient	standard error	Beta		
Frim	22.42	.067	0.658	20.264	0.000
Maid leadership	.698	.016		44.255	0.000

Source: By researchers using Calculator Output:

The table of contrast analysis and transaction table for the relationship between the (X) intellectual capital and the study sample level of(127) people show that the T is greater when compared to its tabular value, the (0.05) and the (1,129) bastions, indicating that the slope curve is sufficient to describe the relationship between (X,Y). At the level of confidence ((0.95),which is confirmed by the meaning value (x) and by the test (t), it was (t=20.264).

In light of the regression equation the constant (a=2.422) is indicated, meaning that there is an intellectual capital presence of(2.422) when the value of the maid's leadership is worth zero.

The value of the slope was ($\beta=0.658$) and associated with (x) indicates that a change of (1) in the x leadership would result in a change of (0.658) in intellectual capital.

The value of the coefficient of determination (R²) also indicates a factor of (0.74), which means that the leading command (x) interprets its value (0.74) from the variation in intellectual capital,The unexplained variation (0.26) is due to variables that have not entered the regression model, an acceptable indicator of a calculated value (F) that is greater than its tabular value of (4.00) in a significant level (0.05) and in light of these results this hypothesis is accepted.

5.2. Subhypothesis testing: After the hypothesis tests the main effect, it is necessary to test the impact of leadership (conceptual skills, empowerment, subordinates' assistance, ethics, emotional treatment, commitment to community development) on intellectual capital.

According to this hypothesis, the multiple regression equation for the driving driving variables (x₁, x₂, x₃, x₄, x₅, x₆) in intellectual capital (y) is in terms of the following multiple regression equation:

$$Y = a + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6$$

The multiple regression equation of the relationship between the Servant leadership (x) and intellectual capital was:

Intellectual capital = (1.899) + (0.42) Conceptual skills + (0.33) enabling + (0.31) supporting subordinates + (0.28) acting ethic + (0.34) emotional treatment + (0.39) commitment to community development.

Table(3) referred to the values shown and as follows:

Table (3) the results of the test of influence relationships between the dimensions of Servant leadership in intellectual capital.

model	Non-standard transactions		standard transactions	T	Sig
	Beta coefficient	standard error	Beta		
Frim	1.899	.083	0.42	16.021	0.000
Conceptual skills	.361	.034		12.624	0.000
enabling	.423	.024	0.33	14.876	0.000
supporting subordinates	.166	.034	0.31	7.733	0.000
acting ethic	.264	.044	0.28	8.731	0.000
emotional treatment	.169	.014	0.34	9.734	0.000
Commitment to community development	.186	.032	.390	9.533	0.000

Source: Researchers based on the results of the electronic calculator.

It is clear from the table (3) that the regression equation indicates the constant (a=1.899), which means that there is a intellectual capital presence of 1.899) when the value of the dimensions of the maid drive is zero.

The value of the finalist tendency to distance conceptual skills has reached ($\beta_1=0.42$) and acolym for (X₁) indicates that a change of (1) in conceptual skills (X₁) would lead to a positive change of (0.42) in intellectual capital.

The value of the enabling dimension's "finalist propensity" ($\beta_2=0.33$) and accompanying X2 indicates that a change of (1) in empowerment (X2) would lead to a positive change of (0.33) in intellectual capital.

The value of the remote tendency of assisting subordinates ($\beta_3=0.31$) and accompanying x3 indicates that a change of (1) in helping subordinates (x3) would lead to a positive change of (0.31) in intellectual capital.

The value of the depository of the deed behavior has reached ($\beta_4 =0.28$) and accompanying (X4) indicates that a change of (1) in the behavior of ethics (X4) will lead to a positive change of (0.28) in intellectual capital.

The value of the deaf of emotional treatment dimension ($\beta_5=0.34$) and accompanying (X5) indicates that a change of (1) in emotional treatment (X5) would lead to a positive change of (0.34) in intellectual capital.

The value of the strict tendency of the commitment to community development ($\beta_6=0.39$) and accompanying (X6) indicates that a change of (1) commitment to community development (X6) will lead to a positive change of (0.39) in intellectual capital.

On the basis of these findings all subassumptions of Servant leadership in intellectual capital are accepted.

6. Conclusions

The literature suggests that Servant leadership negatively affects organizations' overall performance, as the search results show that the leadership's virtuous characteristics of its indicators were to a degree High in the administrative Servant leadership of the Kufah University Foundation, The managing leader is contributing to To have those who work with him have the necessary qualifications to perform his work, and encourage others to take the reins Initiative. Intellectual capital may also lead to easy access to customers and investors, thereby enhancing the overall performance of organizations. The study examined whether the leadership leads to a lack of intellectual capital, in this study the Servant leadership between the leadership that formed from six indicators, namely conceptual skills, empowerment, the concern of subordinates for development and success, the behavior of ethics, Emotional treatment and commitment to community development and its relationship to intellectual capital. We encourage our colleagues in the provinces and other countries to repeat our study in order to test whether our results are the same in each governorate and country or other variables can be added or improved. We urge researchers to conduct further research on this subject in other institutions that will greatly enhance our understanding of Servant leadership.

Reference:

- Adesina K.S. Bank technical, allocative and cost efficiencies in Africa: The influence of intellectual capital. *North American Journal of Economics and Finance* 8 (2019) pp 419- 433.
- Andrea , Lantu D.C. Servant Leadership and Human Capital Management: Case Study in Citibank Indonesia. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 169 (2015) 303 – 311.
- Appelbaum S.H, Karasek R, Lapointe F, Quelch K. Employee empowerment: factors affecting the consequent success or failure – Part I. *Industrial and Commercial Training*. (2014) . Vol. 46 Iss 7pp. 379 – 386.
- Bauera T.N, Perrotb S, Lidenc R.C, Erdogan B. Understanding The Consequences Of Newcomer Proactive Behaviors: The Moderating Contextual Role Of Servant Leadership. *Journal Of Vocational Behavior* 112.(2019).p356-368, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.05.001>.
- Belizón J.d. F, Alcázar F.M, Gardey G.S. Conceptualizing academic intellectual capital: definition and proposal of a measurement scale. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*. (2019) . <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIC-09-2018-0152>.
- Chi Zou W, Tian Q, Liu J. Servant leadership, social exchange relationships, and follower's helping behavior: Positive reciprocity belief matters. *International Journal of Hospitality Management* 51 (2015) 147–156.
- Chiniara M , Bentein K. The servant leadership advantage: When perceiving low differentiation in leader-member relationship quality influences team cohesion, team task performance and service OCB. *The Leadership Quarterly journal homepage*(2017) : www.elsevier.com/locate/leaqua.
- Eva N, Robinb M, Sendjayac S, Dierendonckd D.V , Lidene D.C. Servant Leadership: A systematic review and call for future research. *The Leadership Quarterly journal homepage*(2018): www.elsevier.com/locate/leaqua .
- Gautam D. K, Ghimire S. B. Psychological Empowerment of Employees for Competitive Advantages: An Empirical Study of Nepalese Service Sector. *International Journal of Law and Management*. (2017). Vol. 59 Issue:4, doi: 10.1108/IJLMA-03-2016-0035.
- Howard A. Positive and negative emotional attractors and intentional change. *Journal of Management Development*. (2006) .Vol. 25 Iss 7pp. 657 – 670.
- Howard A. Positive and negative emotional attractors and intentional change. *Journal of Management Development*. (2006). Vol. 25 Iss 7 pp. 657 – 670.
- Jagtap S. Key guidelines for designing integrated solutions to support development of marginalised societies. *Journal of Cleaner Production*.(2019). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.01.340>.
- Kengatharan N. k, A knowledge-based theory of the firm: Nexus of intellectual capital, productivity and firms' performance. *International Journal of Manpower*. (2019) . <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJM-03-2018-0096>.

- Koseoglu G, Liu Yi , Shalley C.E. Working with creative leaders: Exploring the relationship between supervisors' and subordinates' creativity *The Leadership Quarterly* . journal homepage(2017). www.elsevier.com/locate/leaqua .
- Pandita D, Singh M, Choudhary S. The Changing Dynamics of Manager-Subordinate Relationships in Organizations: An Empirical Study. *European Business Review*. (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-04-2017-0072>.
- Quan Li Y, Liuc.H.S. The Role Of Problem Identification And Intellectual Capital In The Management Of Hotels' Competitive Advantage-An Integrated Framework. *International journal Of Hospitality Management*.(2018). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhm.2018.05.022>.
- Rachmawati A. W, Lantu D. C. The 5th Indonesia International Conference on Innovation, Entrepreneurship and Small Business (IICIES 2013) . *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 115 (2014) 387 – 393 .
- Riley L. S, Kohlbacher F. Ethically minded consumer behavior: Scale review, development, and validation. *Journal of Business Research*(2015) .
- Stollberger J, Heras M.L, Rofcanin Y , Bosch M. J. Serving followers and family? A trickle-down model of how servant leadership shapes employee work performance. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2019.02.003>.
- Tost L.P, Johnson H. Huang .The prosocial side of power: How structural power over subordinates can promote social responsibility. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes* 152 (2019) 25–46 .
- Yong J.Y , Yusliza M.Y, Ramayah T, Fawehinmi O. Nexus between green intellectual capital and green human resource management. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 215 (2019) 364-374.
- Yusoff Y. M, Omar M.K , Zaman M. D. K, Samad S. Do all elements of green intellectual capital contribute toward business sustainability? Evidence from the Malaysian context using the Partial Least Squares method. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 234 (2019) 626-637.
- Zhao G, Chen Ya-Ru , Brockner J. What influences managers' procedural fairness towards their subordinates? The role of subordinates' trustworthiness. *Journal of Experimental Social Psychology* 59 (2015) 96–112 .

Author Information

Ahmed Fadhil Salman

Babylon Education Directorate

Hayder Jasim Obaid

Faculty Of Administration & Economics , University of Kufa

Ihsan Abdulmeer Azeez

Faculty Of Computer Sciences and Maths , University of Kufa

Mohanad Hameed Yasir

Faculty Of Administration & Economics , University of Kufa .